

Mathematizing at Work: Documenting Ilonggo Weavers' Mathematics Concepts in Bamboo Crafts

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Abstract:- This case study was conducted in Maasin, Iloilo, the Philippines, to ascertain the weavers' way of life, particularly the mathematical concepts embodied in their weaving practices. This study documented mathematics concepts and competencies included in the K to 12 Mathematics curriculum the weavers exhibited. A holistic multiple case study design with a single unit of analysis was employed in this study. Participant observations and in-depth interviews were used with the three purposively chosen informants. The researcher utilized field notes, observation guides, recorded videos, photographs, and artifacts for triangulation and analysis. The mathematics concepts revealed from the weavers are basic arithmetic, estimation, dimension, perimeter and circumference, patterns, congruence, parallelism, perpendicularity, geometric figures, and polygons. The weavers manifest mathematical content standards on key concepts and skills involving numbers, Four Fundamental Operations, Non-standard and standard measures of length and mass, the idea of perimeter and circumference, the concept of measurement, continuous patterns, lines, and symmetrical designs, parallel and perpendicular lines, and quadrilaterals, and polygons, circles, and solid figures. Recommendations on embedding weaving activities in mathematics instruction were discussed.

Keywords:- Mathematics Education, Mathematics concepts, case study, Ilonggo weavers, bamboo crafts.

I. INTRODUCTION

The United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organizations (UNESCO) are categorized into three the purpose of mathematics in everyday life (Quadling, 1982). First, survival mathematics is the mathematics we need to go about our daily business, such as paying the fare on a bus, cooking, etc. Second, —mathematics for use describes all the job-specific mathematics, and only a minority of people will ever use it- such as mathematics for engineers, navigators, and pharmacists. Third, mathematicians' mathematics deals with logical reasoning in teaching mathematics from a practical perspective that a little-remembered knowledge could produce a large amount of derived knowledge. These facts suggest that mathematics is present in our day-to-day activities, and it is essential in our society.

However, the means and ways in which some mathematics educators presented their lessons and the unavailability of materials needed to teach the mathematics concepts to the students posed problems in understanding its

practical applications. How mathematics concepts are introduced to the learners devoid of daily application is the root cause of students' present scenario finding difficulty understanding these concepts. Many students argue that most of the concepts they learned in the classroom have no significance in their day-to-day lives. This scenario is one of the perceived reasons why some students have low motivation and interest in learning the subject. This situation led to Filipino students' poor academic performance in the international standardized test and students' lack of interest in learning. This result is reflected in the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), where the Philippines have dismal results. Among 79 participating countries or economies, the Philippines ranked dead last in reading and ranked second last in mathematics and science (Schleicher, 2019).

These realities gave me an idea to pursue a study that will highlight the essence of the contextualization and localization of mathematics lessons through investigating its practical application in handicrafts making, which can be found in the locality. It aimed to provide detailed explanations of how the mathematics concepts were utilized in the Ilonggo weavers' livelihood activities. Students can grasp that mathematics is present in our day-to-day activities through the contextualization and localization of mathematics lessons. As reflected in the Department of Education's mission, to protect and promote every Filipino's right to quality, equitable, culture-based, and complete basic education (Department of Education, 2014).

The Philippines is the second-largest world producer of handicrafts, mainly baskets out of indigenous materials (Colosus Handicraft, 2015). Handicrafts such as baskets, brooms, feather dusters, bamboo sofa sets, cabinets, and other furniture were some of Filipino weavers' innovative products. The province of Iloilo has an abundant supply of bamboo poles. Around 8, 085 hectares are planted with bamboo producing 2,426,487 poles every year, with the municipality of Maasin devoting 3,000 hectares for bamboo farming (my beautiful LOILO, 2014). Due to its abundance in the locality, these bamboos were utilized by the Ilonggo weavers in weaving and crafting bamboo crafts.

This study involved the exploration of the mathematics concepts in the weaving practices of the Ilonggo weavers. It ascertained the mathematical concepts and skills applied by Ilonggo weavers as they construct meaning on these mathematics concepts and skills. These meanings were constructed through the interpretation of the Ilonggo weavers involved or the researcher's analysis; thus, this study was apt

to anchor on constructionism as its epistemological perspective and symbolic interactionism as its theoretical perspective.

Crotty (1998) agrees that constructionism claims that human beings in the environment are involved with construct meanings. He stated that constructionism is an epistemology that deals with constructing meanings as one interacts with the object. The meanings that people create are contingent on their encounters with the world and others (Flick, 2009). My life revolves around educating the learners' young minds while the weavers spin their lives on their bamboo crafts. They have different purposes for doing things and different meanings for things that seem familiar to my knowledge, just like measurement, priorities, and routines. Hence, it was apt to engage in the weavers' world to understand their experiences better as they engaged in bamboo crafts making.

Meanwhile, symbolic interactionism served as the theoretical stance where this study is anchored. As Herbert Blumer claimed, symbolic interactionism is the process of interaction in the formation of meanings for individuals (Nelson, 1998). In this study, these interactions referred to the encounters, teaching moments, and interactions of the Ilonggo weavers with their environment. This answered the questions of how they look at the value of resources, how they learned the process of making bamboo crafts, and their interactions with other people who enhance their skills. These meanings constructed by the Ilonggo weavers are handled and modified through an interpretive process used by the person in dealing with the things he encounters (Blumer in Crotty, 1998).

Crotty (1998) expounded that there are four essential elements to be considered when conducting social research – the methods we propose to use, the methodology that governs the choice and use of methods, and the theoretical perspective behind the methodology epistemology that informs the theoretical perspective. Figure 1 shows the relationship among the four essential elements that inform one another. The figure further illustrates the connection of constructionism as the study's epistemology, symbolic interactionism as the theoretical perspective, case study as the methodology, and the use of different methods in collecting the data.

Fig. 1: Epistemology, theoretical perspective, methodology, and methods employed in the study.

This study aimed to provide a detailed elucidation on the link between mathematics and the weaving of bamboo crafts of the Ilonggo weavers. This also pertained to

observing and identifying the Ilonggo weaver's creation of meaning on mathematics concepts as they engaged in weaving bamboo crafts. Specifically, it sought to answer the following research questions: (1) What mathematics concepts did the Ilonggo Weavers utilize in weaving bamboo crafts? and (2) What learning competencies in the K to 12 Mathematics Curriculum need to be mastered by Ilonggo Weavers to enhance the efficacy and efficiency of their work?

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Methodological Perspective

Case study research design, specifically, a holistic multiple case study design with a single unit of analysis, is meant to provide detailed explanations of the mathematical concepts utilized in weaving bamboo crafts (Yin, 2009). In this case, the context is the bamboo crafts, the three weavers served the case of this study, and the single unit of analysis is the mathematics concepts. A qualitative inquiry embedded in this research satisfied the given characteristics of Merriam (1998) about the case study: particularistic, heuristic, and descriptive.

B. Informants

The informants of the study were three makers of bamboo crafts. These weavers were chosen as informants because of their knowledge and expertise in making the products and their exposure and experiences in the industry. The three weavers involved in this study were selected from the list of probable informants using Expedient Selection. Expedient selection means choosing appropriate, available, and interested participants to engage in the research (Freebody, 2003). The informants of this study were those who were qualified in the tentative selection criteria that I prepared.

C. Procedure

The exploration phase was a preparatory stage wherein the things needed were prepared before going into the field. This comprised gathering a review of related literature, finding data sources, gaining access to the setting, selecting key informants, and preparing research instruments. The use of multiple sources of evidence in case studies allows an investigator to address a broader range of historical and behavioral issues (Yin, 2009). Data were gathered through participant observation, in-depth interviews, field notes, taking photographs, and video recording.

For the researcher to deeply understand the process of making bamboo crafts and the informant's way of life, participant observation and in-depth interviews were conducted as espoused by Spradley (1980). The researcher engaged himself in the locality to learn the basics of bamboo crafts making and gain sufficient understanding to integrate into mathematics lessons. During this study, the researcher wrote down his reflections and observations on how the weavers crafted bamboo crafts. The interview is a means to elicit oral responses from the informants and allowed the researcher to create meanings on the mathematical concepts embedded in the bamboo crafts. The researcher prepared interview questions before the interview schedule. During the interview sessions, the researcher asked the informants to use

audio and video recording devices to capture the necessary data. Photos of bamboo crafts were taken to serve as one of the bases for the interpretation of concepts.

All the data made sense of it and was organized into categories or themes that cut across all data sources. A discussion of qualitative data was based on the themes that emerged from the gathered data. Hence, qualitative data analysis involved thematic analysis (Braune & Clark, 2006). It includes a step-by-step guide comprised of familiarizing with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and producing the report. Multiple sources were used to triangulate the results. Triangulation helped crosscheck and was used to provide confirmation and completeness.

The researcher ensured that all the data gathered from the informants were used only for the purpose of conducting the study and not for anything else. To keep the confidentiality of the information and documents provided by my informants, all the data from the conduct of this study were stored in a secure and safe place so that no one who is not meant to access the data can see it. For the recorded observations of the dialogue in the sessions and the interviews' responses, pseudonyms were used to name the respondents. The researcher secured a conforme signed by informants that they agreed to participate in the study. To avoid bias in the result, the researcher was careful in collecting and analyzing the data to ensure the results' consistency.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Thinking mathematically and solving mathematical problems successfully are skills, which evolve in the course of learning mathematics in a school context, as well as in an everyday context. However, how mathematics concepts are utilized in every individual's daily activity and how it applies in the practice of different professions and vocations is still a question to some people. Through participant observations and a series of in-depth interviews, the informants revealed that they manifested Mathematical skills in weaving the bamboo crafts.

The mathematical meanings were generated from the informants' narratives and based on the researcher's participant observations. The meanings created by the informants were taken into account by the researcher to determine what mathematical concepts and how it was embedded in weaving the bamboo crafts.

A. Mathematical Concepts Embedded in Weaving Bamboo Crafts

The study's findings have shown that the weavers possess mathematical competencies in Numbers and Number Sense, Measurement, Patterns and Algebra, and Geometry. The weavers had used mathematical concepts such as basic arithmetic, estimation, dimensions, patterns, congruence, parallelism, perpendicularity, geometric figures, and polygons in their weaving practices as weavers of bamboo crafts.

Basic Arithmetic. The three informants used basic counting to determine the numbers of strips need to weave a certain bamboo craft. The counting of the bamboo strips was emphasized at the start of the weaving process since knowing the number of strips is essential for them to learn to weave the bamboo craft. The use of four fundamental operations, such as addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division, were highlighted.

Estimation. Estimations are also used in weaving bamboo crafts. Estimating whether the bamboo strips are already dry and ready for the weaving was emphasized. In determining the desired measurement of the strips to use and the dimension of the products to produce was estimated by the weavers. *Nong Berto* applied the concept of estimations in his job as a weaver when he expounded that, "*ginabantabanta ko malang ran kung mala na ang sukdap.*" [I just estimate if the bamboo strips are already dry.] This is confirmed by *Airely* as she asserts that estimations are present in her works as she mentioned that, "*ginalantaw lang na namon kung mara dun, mabal-an mo man na kung mala na ang sukdap kay naga mag-an na iya bug-at. Tapos, kung green pa ang itsura na hindi pa na mara, pero kung malasaw na nga pagkagreen mara dun day-a.*" [we check it if it is dry already, you can know if the strips are dry already if the weight is not heavy as before, and if the color is still green, then it is not yet dry, but if the color is light green then it is dry already].

Dimension. Determining the bamboo crafts dimensions for production was emphasized since the size of the strips to use depends on it. The informants exhibited the skills to determine the measurements of the products in square, circular, rectangular, and cylindrical shapes. There are techniques that the weavers use to measure the needed sizes to weave in faster and more convenient ways. Instead of measuring the sides of the "*kararaw*" to determine its dimension, *Airely* explains that the size of the "*kararaw*" is determined by measuring the distance between the two nonadjacent corners. "*Magsukol ikaw sir sang size sang kararaw, takson mo ang kalabaon sang duha ka pusod nga nagapaekis*" [When you measure the size of "*kararaw*", you must measure the distance between the two nonadjacent corners]. *Airely* explains that the dimensions of the "*kararaw*" they weave depend on the order made by their clients, and the size is determined by measuring the distance between two corners of the "*kararaw*." Figure 3 shows how the dimension of the "*kararaw*" is being measured. The line connecting the two corners is the size of the "*kararaw*."

Fig. 3: The size of the "*kararaw*" is determined by measuring the distance between two nonadjacent corners

Perimeter and Circumference. The definition and concept of perimeter and circumference were also implicit in weaving bamboo crafts. The informants used their knowledge of perimeter and circumference to determine the strips' length needs to frame the various forms of bamboo crafts. *Airely* applies her understanding of determining the required size of "*uhay*" required to frame the "*kararaw*". The "*uhay*" is a vine, which can be found in most the trees. She said that this vine was utilized after weaving the "*kararaw*" since it needs a frame. The frames serve as the weaving lock and are an essential part of the "*kararaw*". The concept of determining the perimeter is central to *Airely* since it requires her to use this concept to select the desired length of the vein needed in a certain "*kararaw*".

Patterns. Patterns are an inevitable part of weaving bamboo crafts, as revealed by my informants. These different patterns make their products attractive to the customers' eyes that making the bamboo crafts does not solely rely on their quality but also on their physical appearance, the attractiveness. The quality and the beauty of the products were reliant on the patterns used in weaving; hence, patterns and art are not mutually exclusive as my three informants claim that the patterns add beauty to their crafts.

Congruence. Congruency of the materials used in the weaving of bamboo crafts matters to produce quality products. My three informants told me that there must be an equal length of the bamboo strips to use so that it would be easier to weave simultaneously to lead to the product's accurate dimensions. The concept of congruence is also vital in making the food tray frames as the bamboo strips that were cut into two parts, the inner and outer, must be congruent and must be aligned together. The strips must be congruent so that the edges or the sides of the bamboo ceiling are straight and aligned. The linear alignment of the edges throughout the weaving is desired for the bamboo ceilings. The congruence in terms of the strips' length is necessary since it is essential in the process to have an accurate form of the "*kararaw*."

Parallelism. Establishing parallelism in weaving is essential to make sure that the placing of the strips is "*himpot*" (neat), with no "*harat*" or hole. Once there is a "*harat*," the quality of the product is at risk. The emphasis on utilizing the concept of parallelism is essential in weaving the bamboo crafts for dimension accuracy. The concept of parallelism in weaving the bamboo placemat is present in weaving the 1-under-1-over-1 pattern, that the strips must be equidistant from each other. The strips must be parallel to the other strips to establish the beauty of the bamboo placemat. The proper placing of the strips equidistant to other strips will create holes that put beauty on the placemat. In weaving the "*kisame*" or bamboo ceilings, Joan also reveals the importance of the strips' parallelism to ensure that her weaving is neat and intact. She mentioned that "*dapat kung magrara ikaw, dapat patas ran ang distansya sang mga sukdap nimo, dapat himpot guid*. [when you weave, the strips' distance must be the same to ensure that the strips are intact].

Fig. 4: An improvised hammer and bamboo stick were used to make the strips intact.

Fig. 5: Establishing parallelism by making a square pattern.

Perpendicularity. The perpendicularity of the strips may be considered as part of the design of the products. At the same time, the quality of the product produced is dependent on adequately establishing the perpendicularity of the strips. In weaving bamboo crafts, horizontal and vertical lines are emphasized. When these lines intersect in the process of weaving, the concept of perpendicularity is present. The formation of the right-angle image was evident when the horizontal and vertical strips intersected each other. The intersection of the horizontal and vertical strips and the right-angle formation unveils the concept of perpendicularity.

Fig. 6: Presence of the intersection of vertical and horizontal lines in the "*kararaw*".

Geometric figures. Geometric figures and relationships have played an essential role in society's sense of what is aesthetically pleasing. Geometric figures and polygons are apparent in the various products of the three research informants. The use of varied polygons for placemats such as circles, squares, diamonds, and other shapes is evident in the weavers' works. The right angle was formed when the two types of strips, the shorter and the longer ones or the horizontal and verticals strips, intersected perpendicularly. At the start of the weaving process, the first step is to fold the strips into two parts, making the two endpoints aligned

together. The folding of the strips into two equal parts, the midpoint of the strip is determined.

Polygons. Polygons can be seen in the woven products of the weavers. Squares, rectangles, circles, and rhombus are present in my three informants' bamboo crafts. The polygons are present in the "bilao", table placemat, and decorative materials, "kararaw", bamboo ceiling, "aryagan", "tabig," and "bandi". Squares are present in the decorative materials, and bamboo placemats of *Nong Berto*. Squares are also evident in the "kararaw" of *Airely* and "aryagan" of *Joan*.

Fig. 7: Squares found in the decorative materials, bamboo placemats, "aryagan", and "kararaw".

B. K to 12 Mathematics Learning Competencies Embodied in the Weavers' Weaving Practices

Weavers showed the mathematics concepts they exhibited in weaving the bamboo crafts, and this is patterned to the content standard and learning competencies in the K to 12 Mathematics Curriculum. The weavers have shown competence in the content areas such as numbers and number sense, measurement, patterns and algebra, and geometry. The following were the weavers' content standards that must be mastered to enhance the efficacy and efficiency of their works. The weaver or the learner demonstrates understanding and appreciation of:

Key concepts and skills involving numbers. Key concepts and skills involving numbers consist of visualizing and representing numbers, counting, and grouping the number of objects in a given set by ones and tens, and visualizing and counting numbers by 2s, 5s, 10s, 50s, and 100s.

Four Fundamental Operations. Four Fundamental Operations include illustrating addition as —putting together or combining or joining sets; visualizing and stating basic multiplication facts for numbers up to 10; visualizing division of numbers up to 100 by 6, 7, 8, and 9; visualizing and stating basic division facts of numbers up to 10; dividing 2- to 3-digit numbers by 1- to 2- digit numbers without and with remainder; dividing 2-3 digit numbers by 10 and 100 without or with remainder; performing addition and

subtraction of similar and dissimilar fractions; describing and interpreting the basic operations on integers using materials such as algebra tiles, counters, chips, and cards; and performing the basic operations on integers.

Non-standard and standard measures of length and mass. This contains estimating and measuring length using non-standard units of linear measurements and mass measure; measuring objects using appropriate measuring tools in m or cm; estimating and measuring length using a meter or centimeter and estimating and measuring mass using a gram or kilogram.

Concept of perimeter and circumference. This is comprised of finding the perimeter of triangles, squares, rectangles, parallelograms, and trapezoids; Visualizing the circumference of a circle; measuring the circumference of a circle using appropriate tools; deriving a formula for finding the circumference of a circle, and finding the circumference of a circle.

Concept of Measurement. This includes illustrating what it means to measure and approximating the measures of quantities, particularly the length, weight/mass, volume, time, angle, temperature, and rate.

Continuous patterns. This consists of determining the missing term/s in a given continuous pattern using one attribute (letters/ numbers/events); and determining the missing term/s in a given repeating pattern using one attribute (letters, numbers, colors, figures, sizes, etc.).

Lines and symmetrical designs. This comprises recognizing and drawing a point, line, line segment, and ray; recognizing and drawing parallel, intersecting, and perpendicular lines; visualizing, identifying, and drawing congruent line segments.

Concepts of parallel and perpendicular lines, and quadrilaterals. This includes describing, illustrating parallel, intersecting, and perpendicular lines, identifying, and describing the different kinds of quadrilaterals: square, rectangle, parallelogram, trapezoid, and rhombus.

Polygons, circles, and solid figures. This contains visualizing and describing congruent polygons, circle, and solid figures; visualizing and describing different solid figures: cube, prism, pyramid, cylinder, cone, and sphere; and differentiating solid figures from plane figures; illustrating the different solid figures using various concrete and pictorial models; and visualizing and describing the different solid figures: cube, prism, pyramid, cylinder, cone, and sphere.

Key concepts of quadrilaterals (parallelograms, trapezoids, kites) and triangle similarity. This involves identifying the quadrilaterals that are parallelograms; determining the conditions that guarantee a quadrilateral parallelogram; and using properties to find the measures of angles, sides, and other quantities involving parallelograms.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The result of the study introduces implications to theory and practice. The finding of the research implies the theory of Bishop's (2002) mathematical acculturation. Bishop (1988) claims that despite the variation in how each society develops and applies mathematics, every society's cultural activity can be universally classified into counting, locating, measuring, designing, playing, and explaining. These activities are mathematical in nature. As a result, mathematics and the art in the local craftsmen's weaving practices are not mutually exclusive. By engaging in weaving activities with other weavers and constant practice of crafting the bamboo products, mathematics skills are developed and learned. Mathematics is present in the bamboo products made and present in the daily activities of the weaver.

Several implications for practice flow from the findings of this study. Teach mathematics concepts and skills by applying strategies that are contextualized to the learners' environment. Contextualizing and concretizing the lesson to the learner's environment provides them with better comprehension and application of the concepts to other life situations. Using concrete manipulative materials using bamboo crafts is one way of contextualizing and concretizing the mathematics lessons. Introducing the mathematics concepts to the learners with the aid of concrete manipulative as a form of indigenization of the concept will help the learners grasp the understanding of the concepts and appreciate the practicality of mathematics. When the learners understand that learning these mathematical concepts is needed to master and do a particular job, motivation and the desire to learn come in. Introducing the lesson to the learners leading to understanding and appreciating its life purpose will enable them to motivate and quest for knowledge.

This case study provides the teachers with knowledge and techniques in teaching mathematics more engagingly through contextualizing and concretizing mathematics concepts. This provides opportunities for curriculum makers to open a discussion to include contextualizing the mathematical concepts in the curriculum. It may pave the way for the curriculum designers to use instructional materials such as indigenous handicrafts in the curriculum by advancing a positive impact on the teaching-learning process. Instructional materials developers may highlight teaching strategies in learning mathematical concepts that are more student-centered and culturally sensitive materials from a constructivist perspective, such as incorporating indigenous handicrafts through hands-on activities.

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